

Comparison of Activation Function with CNN for Cat vs Dog Image Classification

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Abstract—This study discusses the comparison between activation functions using Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). This comparison will be used to classify images, namely cats and dogs. Some of the activations that will be compared are relu, sigmoid, softmax, softplus, softsign, and selu. It is necessary to know the difference between the level of accuracy and the level of error to classify images. In addition, a comparison will also be made for each activation using data augmentation. The data sheet will be divided into training data, validation data and test data. The results obtained from this comparison process show that Softsign without augmentation data is better than other activation.

Keywords— *Activation, CNN, Cat, Dog, Data Augmentation*

I. INTRODUCTION

In the current era of technological development, image classification is a universal problem in our life. Various applications for image classification continue to be developed and various products are built to help and simplify human work. This app automatically identifies information related to images until classify their type. This identification and classification use a machine learning model which can learn the appropriate parameters from the data automatically and less manual operation. Machine learning is further developed with the advent of Deep Learning.

Deep learning allows researchers to propose many effective machine learning models and training algorithms. Types of deep learning, especially neural network convolutions, show optimal performance in image classification problems. Research [1] has discussed the classification of images of cats and dogs using CNN and showed good results. Research [2][3] has discussed fruit classification using CNN and Pure-CNN which is able to reduce the error rate and produce high accuracy.

In this paper, researchers use a classification between cats and dogs using one type of Deep Learning, namely Convolution Neural Network (CNN). The dataset used is based on a real-world dataset, but fake images are used for the test data. Researchers also compared various types of activation functions to see the level of accuracy and error rate. To find a better performance, the researcher will discuss the effect of the data augmentation technique on each of these activation functions.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Convolution Neural Network

A convolutional neural network is a multilayer neural network composed of convolutional layers and pooling layers, showing great application prospects in the field of image recognition. Such a network can directly use the pixel matrix of the image as the input value, and extract the abstract features through the training process of the neural network, thus improving the accuracy of the classification and recognition task. In addition, convolutional layers and pooling layers, the special structures in the network, can significantly reduce the scale of image data and the number of parameters, thus lowering the structural complexity of the neural network. In the design of the network structure, however, a series of network structure parameters such as batch size, learning rate, and activation function exert an important impact on the training results and efficiency.

B. Data Augmentation

The data augmentation technology generates similar but different training samples by making a series of random changes to the training images, thereby expanding the size of the training data set. Randomly changing the training samples can reduce the model's dependence on certain attributes, thereby improving the generalization ability of the model. For example, we can crop the image in different ways to make the object of interest appear in different positions, thereby reducing the dependence of the model on the position of the object. We can also adjust factors such as brightness and color to reduce the model's sensitivity to color. Therefore, we added image recognition technology without changing the model to see if the accuracy of the model has been improved.

C. Activation Function

1. ReLU

The rectified linear activation function, or ReLU activation function, is perhaps the most common function used for hidden layers. It is common because it is both simple to implement and effective at overcoming the limitations of other previously popular activation functions, such as Sigmoid and Tanh. Specifically, it is less susceptible to vanishing gradients that prevent deep models from being trained, although it can suffer from other problems like saturated or “dead” units.

The ReLU function is calculated as follows: $f(x) = \max(0.0, x)$. This means that if the input value (x) is negative, then a value 0.0 is returned, otherwise, the value is returned.

2. Sigmoid

The sigmoid activation function is also called the logistic function. It is the same function used in the logistic regression classification algorithm. The function takes any real value as input and outputs values in the range 0 to 1. The larger the input (more positive), the closer the output value will be to 1.0, whereas the smaller the input (more negative), the closer the output will be to 0.0.

The sigmoid activation function is calculated as follows: $f(x) = 1.0 / (1.0 + e^{-x})$. Where e is a mathematical constant, which is the base of the natural logarithm.

3. Softmax

The softmax function outputs a vector of values that sum to 1.0 that can be interpreted as probabilities of class membership. It is related to the argmax function that outputs a 0 for all options and 1 for the chosen option. Softmax is a “softer” version of argmax that allows a probability-like output of a winner-take-all function. As such, the input to the function is a vector of real values and the output is a vector of the same length with values that sum to 1.0 like probabilities.

The softmax function is calculated as follows: $f(x) = e^x / \sum(e^x)$. Where x is a vector of outputs and e is a mathematical constant that is the base of the natural logarithm.

4. Softplus

The Softplus can be viewed as a smooth’s version of ReLU and can be used to constrain the output of a machine to always be positive. The softplus activation function is calculated as follows: $f(x) = \log(1+\exp(x))$.

5. Softsign

The Softsign function is an activation function which rescales the values between -1 and 1 by applying a threshold just like a sigmoid function. The advantage, that is, the value of a softsign is zero-centered which helps the next neuron during propagating. The softsign activation function is calculated as follows: $f(x) = x/(1+|x|)$.

6. Selu

Scaled Exponential Linear Unit. This activation functions are one of the newer ones, and it serves us on a particularly long appendix (90 pages) with theorems, proofs etc. When using this activation function in practice, one must use `lecun_normal` for weight initialization, and if dropout wants to be applied, one should use AlphaDropout.

The softsign activation function is calculated as follows: $f(x) = \Lambda(x)$ if $x > 0$ dan $f(x) = \Lambda(\alpha \cdot e^x - \alpha)$ if $x \leq 0$

III. DATASET DESCRIPTION

The dataset used is 25200 images of cats and dogs. The image will be divided into several parts. The training data for each cat and dog uses 10625 images. Validation data for each cat and dog uses 1875 images. The test data for each cat and

dog uses 100 images. For this test data using images of fake cats and dogs.

The use of augmentation data is also carried out to compare the accuracy of each activation. This data augmentation causes random changes to the training image, thereby expanding the size of the training data set and reducing the model's dependence on certain attributes.

In this study, the number of iterations (epochs) used was 50 and the steps per epoch used were 100. Researchers used accuracy data and error data as an evaluation model for each activation used. Accuracy is defined as the proportion of correctly classified images to the total number of images.

IV. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

This research uses Jupyter Notebook and utilizes Tensorflow Library for the training, validations and testing processes. Each activation function is executed using an image without augmentation data and an image with augmentation data. Each activation is also run separately.

A. ReLU Activation

By activating ReLU, the accuracy and error rates are obtained, which are shown in the following table.

Training		Validation	
Loss	Accuracy	Loss	Accuracy
7,5814	0,5085	7,9438	0,4850

By using data augmentations obtained the level of accuracy and error rate shown in the table as follows.

Training		Validation	
Loss	Accuracy	Loss	Accuracy
0,6191	0,7303	0,8216	0,7450

The data from the ReLU activation function obtained can state that augmentation data is better seen from the level of accuracy.

B. Sigmoid Activation

By activating Sigmoid, the accuracy and error rates are obtained, which are shown in the following table.

Training		Validation	
Loss	Accuracy	Loss	Accuracy
0,6951	0,5025	0,6931	0,4980

By using data augmentations obtained the level of accuracy and error rate shown in the table as follows.

Training		Validation	
Loss	Accuracy	Loss	Accuracy
0,6942	0,4909	0,6920	0,5256

The data from the Sigmoid activation function obtained can state that augmentation data is better seen from the level of accuracy.

C. Softmax Activation

By activating Softmax, the accuracy and error rates are obtained, which are shown in the following table.

Training		Validation	
Loss	Accuracy	Loss	Accuracy
0,6929	0,5206	0,6929	0,5150

By using data augmentations obtained the level of accuracy and error rate shown in the table as follows.

Training		Validation	
Loss	Accuracy	Loss	Accuracy
0,6931	0,4831	0,6832	0,5056

The data from the Softmax activation function obtained can state that without augmentation data is better seen from the level of accuracy.

D. Softplus Activation

By activating Softplus, the accuracy and error rates are obtained, which are shown in the following table.

Training		Validation	
Loss	Accuracy	Loss	Accuracy
7,5865	0,5025	7,3806	0,5160

By using data augmentations obtained the level of accuracy and error rate shown in the table as follows.

Training		Validation	
Loss	Accuracy	Loss	Accuracy
7,6103	0,5009	7,3959	0,5150

The data from the Softplus activation function obtained can state that without augmentation data is better seen from the level of accuracy.

E. Softsign Activation

By activating Softsign, the accuracy and error rates are obtained, which are shown in the following table.

Training		Validation	
Loss	Accuracy	Loss	Accuracy
0,6864	0,7465	0,9088	0,7630

The data from the Softsign activation function obtained can state that without augmentation data is better seen from the level of accuracy.

F. Selu Activation

By activating Selu, the accuracy and error rates are obtained, which are shown in the following table.

Training		Validation	
Loss	Accuracy	Loss	Accuracy
7,6780	0,4965	7,2739	0,5230

By using data augmentations obtained the level of accuracy and error rate shown in the table as follows.

Training		Validation	
Loss	Accuracy	Loss	Accuracy
0,6820	0,6622	0,5890	0,6882

By using data augmentations obtained the level of accuracy and error rate shown in the table as follows.

Training		Validation	
Loss	Accuracy	Loss	Accuracy
7,4956	0,5141	7,7510	0,4975

The data from the Selu activation function obtained can state that augmentation data is better seen from the level of accuracy.

Overall, the results of running each activation can be combined which is shown in the table as follows:

Running Without Data Augmentation				
Activation	Testing		Validation	
	Loss	Accuracy	Loss	Accuracy
Relu	7,5814	0,5085	7,9438	0,4850
Sigmoid	0,6951	0,5025	0,6931	0,4980
Softmax	0,6929	0,5206	0,6929	0,5150
Softplus	7,5865	0,5025	7,3806	0,5160
Softsign	0,6864	0,7465	0,9088	0,7630
Selu	7,6780	0,4965	7,2739	0,5230

Running Without Data Augmentation				
Activation	Training		Validation	
	Loss	Accuracy	Loss	Accuracy
Relu	0,6191	0,7303	0,8216	0,7450
Sigmoid	0,6942	0,4909	0,6920	0,5256
Softmax	0,6931	0,4831	0,6832	0,5056
Softplus	7,6103	0,5009	7,3959	0,5150
Softsign	0,6820	0,6622	0,5890	0,6882
Selu	7,4956	0,5141	7,7510	0,4975

CONCLUSION

From this research it can be concluded that:

1. By using each activation there is a difference in both the level of accuracy and the level of error.
2. Without augmentation data it is argued that Softsign Activation Function is better than other activities. This is seen from the higher level of accuracy.
3. With augmentation data it is stated that Relu Activation Function is better than other activations. This is seen from a higher level of accuracy.
4. Comparison of all machine learning carried out proves that softsign activation without augmentation data has a higher accuracy and becomes a more optimal activation.

REFERENCES

- [1] Youngjun Lee, "Image Classification with Artificial Intelligence: Cats vs Dogs," 2021 2nd Internasional Conference on Computing and Data Science (CDS), pp 437-441, 2021.
- [2] Naicheng Xu, "Research on the Influence of Convolutional Neural Network Parameters on Fruit Classification", 2019 3rd Internasional Conference on Electronic Information Techology and Computer Engineering (EITCE), pp 606-610, 2019.
- [3] Asia Kausar, Mohsin Sharif, et al, "Pure-CNN: A Framework for Fruit Images Classification", 2018 International Conference on Computational Science and Computational Intelligence (CSCI), pp 404-408, 2018